

Towards Blockchain-enabled Intrusion Detection for Vehicular Navigation Map System

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Abstract. In recent years, with the fast development of autonomous driving technology, the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) has received much more attention regarding the security aspect. The traditional security defense strategies are not enough to cope with the risks faced by the IoV. The mature V2X communication protocols such as C-V2X and DSRC are not widely deployed because they have not reached consensus among telecom operators, vehicle manufacturers, and even governments. In the literature, some researchers proposed to combine blockchain technology, especially consortium blockchain, with IoV. However, we find that the consortium blockchain solution may also face some challenges that once an attacker gains control of permissioned nodes, they can upload fake or false data (e.g., forged geographic information and road information) to affect the system performance and security. Motivated by this issue, this paper focuses on vehicular navigation map and develops a blockchain-enabled intrusion detection scheme for vehicular navigation map systems. It can detect malicious nodes that exist in the blockchain in order to ensure the integrity of navigation map data when uploading.

Keywords: Blockchain technology, Intrusion detection, Internet of Vehicles, Navigation map, Data security, IoV.

1 Introduction

In recent years, with the rapid development of wireless communication, artificial intelligence, Internet of Things (IoT) and other technologies, the world has gradually entered the era of so-called *Industry 4.0*. Almost all industries are trying to use new technologies to carry out technological revolution. In the field of transportation, many countries are preparing for the construction of an intelligent transportation system (ITS) [3,22].

According to the design requirements of the intelligent vehicles, on the basis of using more sensors to make the vehicle more intelligent, the concept of vehicle to everything (V2X) is added as a supplement of sensors, enabling a vehicle to have a more accurate perception of the surrounding environment [8,15]. The V2X technology includes the Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V), Vehicle to Infrastructure

(V2I), Vehicle to Pedestrian (V2P) and Vehicle to Network (V2N) communications. However, more parties in such system may pose a higher security risk. For example, the interface used by V2X in the communication may bring risks to the whole system [1]. The V2X interface could allow an attacker to launch a remote attack and hack the vehicle, i.e., gaining control of the vehicle or the data stored in the vehicle. Meanwhile, mature V2X communication protocols such as C-V2X and DSRC have not been widely deployed, because they did not reach consensus among telecom operators, vehicle manufacturers, and even governments [2]. This is the same for the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) [9], empowered by the adoption of Internet of Things (IoT).

As the information in a V2X network is often decentralized stored and shared between vehicles and infrastructures, some researchers proposed to combine the blockchain technology with vehicular network to ensure the confidentiality and privacy of the shared data. For example, Yuan and Wang [25] discussed the ITS risk and supported the integration with the blockchain technology, in order to ensure the decentralization of the system as well as the integrity and confidentiality of the shared data. However, the blockchain-based solution may still face the risks and attacks due to the adoption of blockchain. As the ITS serves the public infrastructure, it has to be highly secure and subject to some degree of third-party oversight. In this case, there is a need to control whether unknown users can join this network who might be malicious. The consortium blockchain or the private blockchain could be an option [7]. In particular, the private blockchain and the consortium blockchain can set up an enrollment mechanism for the users: the private blockchain only allows one organization to handle the access control, while the consortium blockchain allows more organizations to take the responsibility. Hence, the consortium blockchain should be an expected solution for ITS and IoV to achieve multi-party governance and fulfill the decentralization.

Motivation. Due to the feature of multi-party governance of a consortium blockchain, it can mitigate the impact of some attacks such as the 51% attack. However, with more nodes joining into the consortium blockchain, the risk of internal data leakage will also increase [4,11]. For example, all information in the consortium blockchain can be leaked by one malicious node. In the context of ITS and IoV, navigation map system will provide critical services to help drivers find a destination with a suitable route. However, attackers may take control of some nodes to download and share the wrong map to others via the V2X network. The wrong information (e.g., map update) may lead to traffic congestion, off the right path, and even traffic accidents.

Contribution. The literature has figured out the importance of High-definition (HD) map to the auto-driving cars [23]. Hence, it is believed that maintaining the map integrity and consistence will become an important security standard in the future design of ITS and IoV. Motivated by this observation, we aim to develop a blockchain-enabled intrusion detection approach to protect the vehicular navigation map system. Our contributions can be summarized as below:

- We focus on the detection of malicious nodes in the blockchain-based ITS network, which can share false or wrong navigation maps with other nodes.

Our key idea is to develop a blockchain-enabled intrusion detection approach to detect any false map information shared among vehicles.

- We use the Fabric platform to construct the consortium blockchain-based vehicular network and implement the logic of intrusion detection via smart contract. In the evaluation, we analyze our system performance in terms of detection accuracy and system scalability.

In Section 2, we briefly introduce the background of navigation map system and present related work. Section 3 illustrates the design of our proposed system. Section 4 evaluates the system performance in the aspect of scalability and discusses the limitations. We conclude the work in Section 5.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 High Definition Map

Vehicle-automation system (VAS) is an important part of ITS, while how to locate itself is one of the challenges for auto-driving. A typical solution to mitigate this issue is the cooperative work among GPS, sensors and a high-definition map (HD map) [26]. HD map as a central component of the auto-driving vehicle, it can provide so called “lane-level definition” service to the auto-driving car, which is used to help the intelligent vehicle to gain accurate surrounding information when the sensors cannot feel the environment perfectly in some situations.

Currently, there are two main technical routes for collecting HD map data. One is represented by Google’s mapping car, and the other is represented by Tesla’s FleetLearning Network. It is equivalent to crowd-sourcing mapping tasks by utilizing mass-produced cars to mobilize all the sensors in the fleet to collect and upload data via the cloud to a central database, where eventually each car will be a contributor and a recipient of map data. For this purpose, Zhong *et al.* [27] proposed the combination of blockchain technology with the HD-map update management system. They also introduced a prototype system based on Hyperledger Fabric to allow vehicles uploading the collected data onto blockchain, which can ensure the data integrity and traceability of map update.

However, HD-map is still facing some other threats. Sinai *et al.* [20] presented a Sybil attack against the vehicular navigation system. They trained 15 bots to simulate the vehicles on road, which sent fraud speed data to the server. When driving on a road with 2-8km/h speed, they found that a traffic jam could be caused on the navigation application. Traditionally, the system will recommend the road that is not having jam to the users; however, if the attacker could tamper and falsify map data, then it may lead to a huge security incident. Besides, the attacker could track other users who are using the same application via the malicious vehicles or fake bots. Another attack – Message Falsification Attack [16] can upload forged vehicle locations and events to update the HD map. It is similar to writing dirty data to the database.

2.2 Related Work

The security of ITS and IoV has been widely explored in the literature [21]. With the development of decentralized ledger technology, blockchain has been applied in many different domains, such as data management [10,13], intrusion detection [6,14] and smart city [3,5,12].

In the area of blockchain-based vehicles. Chiu and Meng [3] focused on the Electronic Toll Collection (ETC) system and introduced a blockchain-based ETC system called EdgeTC. Yin *et al.* [24] developed a blockchain-based data storage system to support incremental data updating for intelligent vehicle systems, which can decrease the overhead and enhance data reliability. Vishwakarma and Das [17] introduced an incentive mechanism, called SmartCoin, for vehicles based on a consortium blockchain. Their scheme aimed to mitigate the impact of fraud messages in traffic congestion and road accidents.

For the navigation map system in ITS, Poggenhans *et al.* [19] introduced a HD map framework for the automotive vehicles. They argued that the complex environment in downtown should provide more detailed information on the HD map and then serve the automated vehicles. In fact, the HD map can bring a significant improvement to the automated vehicles. It can not only bring the information services but also mitigate the attacks to the sensors. For instance, if one of the sensors is hacked by sending fraud data to other vehicles (e.g., speed or location), the HD map can provide the correct location data to detect whether the data from the sensor is correct. However, to the best of our knowledge, the robustness of navigation map system was not extensively studied. This motivates our work to explore and enhance the security of map system.

3 Our Proposed System

3.1 System Design

Fig. 1 show the system overview of our blockchain-enabled intrusion detection scheme, including five main entities:

- **Consortium Blockchain:** In our system, consortium blockchain is used to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the data, and also help implement the intrusion detection scheme via smart contract. In addition, the consortium blockchain can provide multi-party maintenance of the system.
- **Certificate Authority (CA):** This is used for the enrollment mechanism of the system. That is, only authorized nodes can connect to the blockchain network. It prevents a large number of malicious nodes from randomly connecting to the network.
- **Intelligent Vehicle:** These vehicles can join the blockchain network as edge nodes with certain computing power. It can calculate the hash value of a map or track and upload the data to the blockchain system. Hence we can use the generated data to detect malicious nodes within the system.

Fig. 1. System overview

- **Road Side Unit (RSU):** This is a device that communicates with On Board Unit (OBU), which can help identify and communicate with vehicles, receiving and forwarding data and other functions. In our system, the RSU mainly provides the communication interface for the vehicles to publish and confirm transactions in the blockchain.
- **Track Recording Unit (TRU):** This unit is a kind of OBU, which can record the vehicle's track path based on GPS. The track path will be an output as a JSON file for usage and storage. In our system, we use the track path as a parameter for our intrusion detection scheme, which validates the places where the vehicle passed.

Below are the main steps on how the system works.

- **Registration.** Each intelligent vehicle and RSU should be registered in the CA with their unique ID (V_{id}, R_{id}) , in order to get the permission to join the consortium blockchain. Once the registration is completed, both of the registered vehicle and the RSU can obtain a certificate and a key pair. Meanwhile, the CA will enroll the registered vehicle and RSU in the system and upload them onto the consortium blockchain.
- **Authentication.** This is the process how an intelligent vehicle establishes a connection with the RSU to join the consortium blockchain. This step proves that a vehicle has indeed passed a particular area at a certain time aiming to prevent malicious nodes from accessing driving tracks and uploading malicious information. It is worth noting that RSU is not trusted by default. When a vehicle enters an area, the RSU initiates the authentication process with the incoming intelligent vehicle. The RSU sends its R_{id} and the signed R_{id} to the intelligent vehicle that is signed by its private key. The vehicle

will validate the signed R_{id} by using the public key of the RSU. After the vehicle has authenticated the RSU, it can encrypt its V_{id} with the vehicle private key by the public key of the RSU, and then can send it to the RSU. The RSU decrypts the received message and validates the signed V_{id} by the public key of the vehicle. Hence, the authentication between the RSU and the vehicle is completed.

- **Transaction.** Once the intelligent vehicle and the RSU complete the authentication step, it can generate data report and push it to the blockchain as a transaction via the RSU. The information to be reported includes: current speed, geographical location, whether there are traffic accidents on the road, and other factors that can influence the navigation decision. The information is collected by the track recording unit on board. All data will be encrypted and sent to the RSU, which will pack the data into transactions and push it onto the blockchain. The consortium blockchain will agree on the transaction based on the selected consensus algorithm.

In this work, we aim to build a consortium blockchain-based vehicular network within a limited region, where vehicles can join dynamically and upload real-time map data (e.g., road conditions, congestion information) and all the data can be stored onto the blockchain. However, it can only ensure that the data will not be tampered during transmission. This is because if the trusted node is compromised, we cannot guarantee that the data uploaded by these compromised nodes is reliable. Therefore, we develop a blockchain-enabled intrusion detection scheme to verify the correctness of data sources and the legitimacy of node operations.

3.2 Threat Model

Before introducing our intrusion detection scheme, we first define the capability of an attacker against the navigation map system as follows. Firstly, the attacker can gain the control of some nodes in the consortium blockchain, i.e., caused by clicking on phishing sites or failing to update the vehicle system. We assume that most of the nodes should update the system regularly, but only a small number of nodes may be vulnerable. Hence, once the attacker obtains the full control of some nodes, they can be used to download the fake map, and share the tampered map data, e.g., road information, to the consortium blockchain. For example, when some malicious nodes exist in the blockchain within a region, they can upload false information about car accidents in that region to the consortium blockchain. If other nodes that are not in the zone receive a false message, they may change the navigation plan. This is similar to a *fake data injection attack* to the navigation map system.

3.3 Blockchain-enabled Intrusion Detection

HD-map is one of the most important factors to ensure the safety of IoV and V2X, such as autonomous vehicles. If someone malicious can share forged map

data, the driving safety of normal vehicles will be seriously affected. Our main idea for building an intrusion detection scheme will be based on the consistency of maps. In particular, we will define normal and malicious nodes within the system according to the legitimacy of uploaded data, so as to identify malicious nodes. The intrusion detection scheme will be implemented via smart contracts deployed on the blockchain.

- **Detection rule.** In our system, we assume that the vehicles will use the same brand’s HD-map, and stipulate the legal behaviors and malicious behaviors based on the consistency of the HD-map in each intelligent vehicle, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Node Behaviors

	Legal node	Malicious node
Map version	Latest Official Version	Unknown/Old Version
Road condition report	Correct	False
Traffic report	Correct	False
POI report	Correct	False
Traffic signs report	Correct	False
Vote	Vote yes for the correct result	Vote No for the correct result

In our scenario, the malicious node acts similarly to one bot node, where external attackers can gain the control of some nodes by means of single point attack, but users themselves do not know that they have been attacked. Hence, the attacker can share and upload forged data with other nodes in the network to affect the driving safety of normal users.

To ensure the consistency of HD-map in our system, every legal node must maintain the latest official version map locally. The malicious node might use a forged map or an old version of HD map to influence the consistency of the map. The real-time data includes the traffic report, road condition report, point of interest (POI) report, and traffic signs report. The legal node must share the correct report, which can be verified by other legal nodes. It means that each kind of map data must be reported and published as a transaction on the blockchain. Therefore, how to identify the reported data becomes the key to distinguish the normal node and the malicious node. In our case, we decide to design a smart contract to realize a double-vote function that can verify the integrity of uploaded data.

- **Detection logic.** Table 2 shows the parameter description, and the detection flow chart is shown in Fig. 2. There is a trigger to start the intrusion detection process, and the main steps are introduced as below.
 1. **Initiation:** One node initiates the voting process by hashing the locally stored map and publishing both *Hash* and *Sender* to call the smart

Fig. 2. Smart Contract Design**Table 2.** Parameter Description

Parameter	Description
Hash	Node's local map version's hash Real-time map data
Sender	Node's unique identifier
IsOrNot	Vote yes or not
Error	Error report of the specific map data
MyHash	Node's track record hash

contract of *vote*. It means that when a node publishes a transaction on the blockchain, other nodes know who initiates a voting process and the transaction detail. The primary goal of this real-name voting is to avoid someone uploading malicious data but the system cannot trace the source of malicious node.

2. **FirstRoundVote:** Once a node starts the voting process, the other nodes should join it. In particular, the nodes have to input their own *Hash* and vote for *yes* or *no* by comparing the local map's hashes with the published *Hash*. If there is a match, then it should vote *yes*, vice versa. Meanwhile, each node has to input their unique identifier in the transaction for real-name voting. Once the system finishes the first round vote, it can perform the consistency check of the local map data among nodes in the network. Therefore, the nodes can be divided into three groups:

- (a) **Vote Yes:** These nodes have the same hash value as the *Hash* in the first step. It means that these nodes are using the same map or uploading the same data as the vote originator.
- (b) **Vote No:** These nodes have a different hash value against the *Hash*. It means that these nodes are using a different map or disagree with the uploaded data from the vote originator.
- (c) **Nonvoters:** These nodes do not join the voting process due to unknown reasons. They might either have Internet connection issues or not join the process on purpose.

According to the detection rule, the malicious nodes will upload false real-time map data or use a non-latest official map. We only need to check the correctness of the initiated *Hash*, then the system can identify which group's nodes are malicious.

3. **SecondRoundVote:** The second round vote is the process that other nodes should verify the correctness of the initiated *Hash*. For the consistency of map version and real-time map data, these nodes should verify the information by themselves and vote their opinion. Therefore, the nodes can also be divided into three groups:
 - (a) **Vote Yes:** These nodes agree with the initiated *Hash*. That is, they have verified the initiated *Hash* and there is no error reported. They also attach the track record as the verification proof. They should input their unique identifier in the transaction for real-name voting.
 - (b) **Vote No:** These nodes disagree with the initiated *Hash*. It means that the result failed to pass the node verification and an error was reported. They also attach the track record as the verification proof.
 - (c) **Nonvoters:** These nodes do not join the vote process due to unknown reasons. They might either have Internet connection issues or not join the process on purpose.

For instance, if the initiated *Hash* is the map version, then other nodes should verify the current map version. If it is unusable such as missing roads, impassable roads, destination incorrectly located and so on, then the node votes *no* to the initiated *Hash* and attaches the node's track record as a proof. The track record is regarded as the proof of verification, it claims that the node does pass a path on map to verify the uploaded data. It is the same solution when the initiated *Hash* is the real-time map data. For the two rounds of voting, each round can divide the nodes into three groups, we thus summarize the relationships into two cases as shown in Fig. 3.

Our voting detection mechanism is based on the principle of majority rule. Once the initiated *Hash* is authenticated, it can identify which groups of nodes are good or malicious from the first and second round vote. However, there are some nonvoters during the voting process. There are two major scenarios: one is for network reasons, and the other is deliberately done by malicious nodes. Due to the complexity, the handling of nonvoters will be addressed in our future work.

Fig. 3. Venn of Nodes

4. **Freezing:** In our system, the countermeasure designed against malicious nodes is freezing. After the second round vote, the system will freeze the malicious nodes, making them unable to participate in blockchain transactions. Hence, malicious nodes cannot impact the consistency and integrity of the system.
- **Detection Scenario.** As shown in Fig. 2, there is a trigger to start the detection process. According to different triggers, we can divide the detection into two conditions: one is the consistency detection of map version, and the other is the consistency detection of data uploaded by nodes. Table 3 shows the description of triggers.

Table 3. Trigger description

Trigger	Map Version	Map Data
Time	When the map company releases the new version	A node reports information about road conditions (traffic jam, accident, POI, etc.)
Area	Limited Area	Limited Area
Initiate Hash	Map version's hash	Reported information's hash

1. **Map version:** For the first scenario, when the map company releases the latest map update, the system should select a random node to start the detection process within a limited area (e.g., a few blocks). It means that only these nodes within the area can join the detection process. This


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root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke successful, result: status:200 payload:"init MapsaleInfo succeed"
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke -o orderer.nap.com:7050 \
-c map -n mapcc --peeraddresses peers.org1.map.com:7051 \
--tls true --cafile /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/map.com/orderers/orderer.nap.com/msp/tlscacerts/tlsca.map.com-cert.pem \
--tlsrootcertfiles /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/org1.map.com/peers/peer0.org1.map.com/tls/ca.crt \
-c ["Args":["seccvote", "0886b273f34fce19d0b804eff5a3f5747ada4ea22f1d49c01e52dbd7875b4b", "0886d66196192554d084d54476de51f9151acd0a9d97cd294a0a3862cad3dd", "1", "1"]]
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke -o orderer.nap.com:7050 \
-c map -n mapcc --peeraddresses peers.org1.map.com:7051 \
--tls true --cafile /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/map.com/orderers/orderer.nap.com/msp/tlscacerts/tlsca.map.com-cert.pem \
--tlsrootcertfiles /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/org1.map.com/peers/peer0.org1.map.com/tls/ca.crt \
-c ["Args":["seccvote", "0886b273f34fce19d0b804eff5a3f5747ada4ea22f1d49c01e52dbd7875b4b", "d88d8cb93b25f543d84244c321745084462942403977893ab7f4494e289262b", "0", "1"]]
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke successful, result: status:200 payload:"Add record succeed"

```

Fig. 5. First Round Vote

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root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke -o orderer.nap.com:7050 \
-c map -n mapcc --peeraddresses peers.org1.map.com:7051 \
--tls true --cafile /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/map.com/orderers/orderer.nap.com/msp/tlscacerts/tlsca.map.com-cert.pem \
--tlsrootcertfiles /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/org1.map.com/peers/peer0.org1.map.com/tls/ca.crt \
-c ["Args":["seccvote", "0886b273f34fce19d0b804eff5a3f5747ada4ea22f1d49c01e52dbd7875b4b", "945e493567554e68f6f2bd5652917269341a513d295a10b7c78c9b9d95dcd", "1", "0", "fee01e2ac4194a9a87f8a8a0c8ebc12a3bc981a929ad5cf810a99e11ae"]]
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke successful, result: status:200 payload:"Add record succeed"
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke -o orderer.nap.com:7050 \
-c map -n mapcc --peeraddresses peers.org1.map.com:7051 \
--tls true --cafile /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/map.com/orderers/orderer.nap.com/msp/tlscacerts/tlsca.map.com-cert.pem \
--tlsrootcertfiles /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/org1.map.com/peers/peer0.org1.map.com/tls/ca.crt \
-c ["Args":["seccvote", "0886b273f34fce19d0b804eff5a3f5747ada4ea22f1d49c01e52dbd7875b4b", "0886d66196192554d084d54476de51f9151acd0a9d97cd294a0a3862cad3dd", "1", "0", "b155dea22e9d0c8dfed038f7d787275775ea40939c146a4e205bcb349ad02f"]]
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke successful, result: status:200 payload:"Add record succeed"
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke -o orderer.nap.com:7050 \
-c map -n mapcc --peeraddresses peers.org1.map.com:7051 \
--tls true --cafile /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/map.com/orderers/orderer.nap.com/msp/tlscacerts/tlsca.map.com-cert.pem \
--tlsrootcertfiles /opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer/crypto/orderOrganizations/org1.map.com/peers/peer0.org1.map.com/tls/ca.crt \
-c ["Args":["seccvote", "0886b273f34fce19d0b804eff5a3f5747ada4ea22f1d49c01e52dbd7875b4b", "d88d8cb93b25f543d84244c321745084462942403977893ab7f4494e289262b", "0", "1", "cc0510e83f9f0312402946f1e11e076f61618a081f5e76d4e4d17783ca"]]
root@ec994868c99:/opt/gopath/src/github.com/hyperledger/fabric/peer# peer chaincode invoke successful, result: status:200 payload:"Add record succeed"

```

Fig. 6. Second Round Vote

- **FirstRoundVote.** Once a node initiates a voting process, the other nodes should join the process. The voting of each node will invoke a smart contract, and the voting process will be regarded as a transaction to be recorded on the chain. Fig. 5 shows the process of a node participating in the first vote. It indicates that *Node 1* agreed with this map but *Node 2* disagreed with the initiated data. To avoid malicious node re-voting in the first round vote, we also implemented a function to ensure that each node can vote only once. Then the system records the address, ballot and the status of all nodes participating in the first round vote. The parameters and descriptions are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Parameters of firstVote

Function: firstVote		
Parameter	Value	Description
Addr	64 bits Hash	Hash of voting node's address
IsOrNot	0,1	0 = node votes no to the init Hash 1 = node votes yes to the init Hash
AddrStatus	0,1	0 = node is frozen 1 = node is active

- **SecondRoundVote.** When a node completes the first round of voting, it has to examine the information being voted. The system assumes that malicious nodes are a small part of all nodes in the system. Hence, we only need to consult a large number of nodes regarding the correctness of the voted information, and determine whether the initialized information is correct. Fig. 6 shows the process of nodes participating in the second round vote.

When the node completes validation of the voted information, the node can invoke the *secVote* function of the smart contract and input parameters as shown in Table 6. The node has to attach its address as the first round vote for real-name voting. It should vote *yes* or *no* for the voted information. Then it should upload the error report and its hash of track record as a proof. We also set up a protection mechanism to prevent the malicious nodes from voting multiple times.

Table 6. Parameters of *secVote*

Function: <i>secVote</i>		
Parameter	Value	Description
Addr	64 bits Hash	Hash of voting node's address
IsOrNot	0,1	0 = node votes no to the init Hash 1 = node votes yes to the init Hash
Error	0,1	0 = There is no error in voted information 1 = There is an error in voted information
MyHash	64 bits Hash	Hash of node's track record

- **Freezing.** According to Fig. 3, there is no matter whether the malicious node or legal node initiates the voting process. Based on the consistency of voted data, the system considers the nodes that oppose the mainstream opinion as malicious nodes in the two voting rounds. The system will freeze the malicious nodes after two rounds of voting.

4.3 Scalability Evaluation

This is an important metric when we evaluate the performance of blockchain-based systems. The scalability issue is mainly caused by the number of nodes, and the number of contract invokes (number of transactions) executed concurrently within the system. We chosen *Solo* as the consensus algorithm in Hyperledger Fabric and stressed our system by using the *Tape* [18] to simulate the multi-node transaction process.

Assumption. As our detection scenario is based on data exchange between vehicles and the blockchain network, our detection does not require a high response speed similar to traditional host-based intrusion detection. It means that we allow the detection finished in several minutes. In addition, our detection will be conducted in phases of two-round voting, so that we can find the relationship between the maximum transaction volume to be processed by all nodes within the current blockchain network in a given period of time. The derivation is shown as below:

- **One node:** During the detection process, one legal node can initiate three transactions at most within the limited time: namely, *init*, *FirstRoundVote*, *SecRoundVote*.

Fig. 7. Dataset information

- **n nodes:** We assume that in the current blockchain network, there are n legal nodes that can join the voting process. Hence, if one node initiates a voting process, then the transactions in the system can be computed as follows:

$$Transactions = 2 \times n \quad (1)$$

- **The worst case:** The worst scenario in the detection process is that all nodes in the system are initiating a voting process concurrently. Then each node should initiate three transactions in the limited time. The transaction volume in this case will reach the system peak as below:

$$Transactions = 3 \times n \times n = O(n^2) \quad (2)$$

Dataset. Based on the relationship that we found between the numbers of nodes and transaction volume above. We designed ten different sets of data to simulate the maximum transaction volume faced by the system. For each dataset, the number of nodes and the maximum transaction are different. We used *Tape* to simulate the process of multi-node transaction packaging and loaded in the blockchain network, and thus explored the generation time of each block and the duration to complete the transaction. The dataset is shown in Fig. 7.

It shows that with the number of nodes in the network increasing, the transaction volume will increase exponentially, which could bring a great challenge to the system.

Result and Analysis. As illustrated in Fig. 8, we used *Tape* to simulate the configured nodes and invoke specific smart contract functions. It can complete the process of transaction packaging and uploading blocks onto the chain, which

is similar in a real-world environment. We thus can get the duration of completing all transactions and the transaction per second (TPS).

```

hhd@vtrkaal-machine:~/go/src/github.com/hyperledger/maf/blockchain/tape$ ./tape --config=confi.yoni --number=300
Time 0.11s Block 2 Tx 10
Time 0.21s Block 3 Tx 10
Time 0.28s Block 4 Tx 10
Time 0.35s Block 5 Tx 10
Time 0.43s Block 6 Tx 10
Time 0.53s Block 7 Tx 10
Time 0.60s Block 8 Tx 10
Time 0.70s Block 9 Tx 10
Time 0.78s Block 10 Tx 10
Time 0.83s Block 11 Tx 10
Time 0.88s Block 12 Tx 10
Time 0.94s Block 13 Tx 10
Time 0.99s Block 14 Tx 10
Time 1.04s Block 15 Tx 10
Time 1.09s Block 16 Tx 10
Time 1.14s Block 17 Tx 10
Time 1.20s Block 18 Tx 10
Time 1.25s Block 19 Tx 10
Time 1.30s Block 20 Tx 10
Time 1.35s Block 21 Tx 10
Time 1.40s Block 22 Tx 10
Time 1.46s Block 23 Tx 10
Time 1.51s Block 24 Tx 10
Time 1.56s Block 25 Tx 10
Time 1.61s Block 26 Tx 10
Time 1.66s Block 27 Tx 10
Time 1.71s Block 28 Tx 10
Time 1.76s Block 29 Tx 10
Time 1.81s Block 30 Tx 10
Time 1.87s Block 31 Tx 10
Tx: 300, duration: 1.85638393s, tps: 160.802866

```

Fig. 8. Experimental case

Once we finished these 10 groups of experiments, we got the trend of duration and TPS with the number of nodes and transactions increasing. The experimental results are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. We can have the following observations:

1. As the number of nodes increases, there was a slight decreasing trend on TPS, but the value decrease would not affect the performance of the system.
2. As there is no significant change in TPS, it can be considered that the speed of transaction processed by the system does not change. Therefore, with the increase of nodes, the amount of transactions will go up.
3. With more nodes, the time of transaction processed by the system can increase significantly, and the time duration may increase exponentially with the increase of transaction volume.

Fig. 9. Duration trend

Fig. 10. TPS trend

Limitation and Discussion. Our system is still under development, and some improvements have to be made in future work.

- We did not solve the challenge on how to handle nonvoters. If we freeze nonvoters, it is very likely that we may freeze legal nodes that cannot vote due to network reasons accidentally. This will reduce the number of legal nodes in the system and undermine the premise of a blockchain system. Hence, we plan to design a new punish mechanism to replace freezing. The basic idea is that we design a credit management system, and each node will have a credit attribute. If a node votes and the majority of the nodes agree with the result, then its credit will increase, and vice versa. If the node does not vote, the credit of the nonvoter will gradually decrease. The credit of the nodes will be taken into account in the voting process, and we can carry out a weighted calculation.

- The current work adopts Solo provided by Fabric, which is a lab-level consensus algorithm with lower performance than the algorithm applied in the actual production (e.g., PBFT, Raft). Hence, we plan to investigate the scalability using commercial consensus algorithms. We also plan to implement a practical network environment to explore the impact of network speed on system scalability.

5 Concluding Remarks

Currently, with the rapid development of intelligent vehicle and autonomous driving, the security of navigation map has become more important. In this work, we developed a blockchain-enabled intrusion detection scheme for vehicular navigation map system, in order to ensure the security of shared map data in the vehicular networks against data tampering and false data uploading. Our intrusion detection scheme adopted the specification-based detection by defining both legal and malicious operations. We also designed a smart contract to realize a two-round voting process. To investigate the system scalability, we conducted a stress test and found that our proposed system could provide good scalability, i.e., with the increasing nodes, there was only a slight decrease on TPS, so that it would not affect the performance of the system.

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References

1. A. Alnasser, H. Sun, J. Jiang: Cyber security challenges and solutions for V2X communications: A survey. *Comput. Networks* 151, pp. 52-67 (2019)
2. I. Agudo, M. Montenegro, J. Lopez: A Blockchain Approach for Decentralized V2X (D-V2X). *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* 70(5), pp. 4001-4010 (2021)
3. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng. EdgeTC - A PBFT Blockchain-based ETC Scheme for Smart Cities. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, vol. 14, pp. 2874C2886 (2021)
4. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng. Mind the Scraps: Attacking Blockchain based on Selfdestruction. In: *Proceedings of The 26th Australasian Conference on Information Security and Privacy (ACISP)*, pp. 451-469 (2021)
5. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng, and W. Li. LibBlock - Towards Decentralized Library System based on Blockchain and IPFS. In: *Proceedings of The 18th International Conference on Privacy, Security, and Trust (PST)*, pp. 1-9 (2021)
6. W. Meng, W. Li, J. Zhou, Enhancing the Security of Blockchain-based Software Defined Networking through Trust-based Traffic Fusion and Filtration. *Information Fusion*, vol. 70, pp. 60-71 (2021)
7. G. Diego. Private blockchain vs consortium blockchain (2021) <https://101blockchains.com/private-blockchain-vs-consortium-blockchain/>
8. K. Ganesan, P.B. Mallick, J. Lohr, D. Karampatsis, A. Kunz: 5G V2X Architecture and Radio Aspects. In: *Proceedings of CSCN*, pp. 1-6 (2019)

9. A. Hbaieb, S. Ayed, L. Chaari: A survey of trust management in the Internet of Vehicles. *Comput. Networks* 203, article 108558 (2022)
10. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng, C.D. Jensen, My Data, My Control: A Secure Data Sharing and Access Scheme over Blockchain. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, vo. 63, 103020 (2021)
11. A. Hofmann, F. Gwinner, A. Winkelmann, C. Janiesch: Security Implications of Consortium Blockchains: The Case of Ethereum Networks. *JIPITEC* 12(4), pp. 1-13 (2021)
12. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng. Towards Decentralized Bicycle Insurance System Based on Blockchain. *The 36th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing (ACM SAC)*, pp. 249-256 (2021)
13. W.Y. Chiu, W. Meng, C.D. Jensen, NoPKI - A Point-to-Point Trusted Third Party Service based on Blockchain Consensus Algorithm. *The 3rd International Conference on Frontiers in Cyber Security (FCS)*, pp. 197-214 (2020)
14. W. Meng, W. Li, L. Zhu. Enhancing Medical Smartphone Networks via Blockchain-based Trust Management against Insider Attacks. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 1377-1386 (2020)
15. S.S. Husain, A. Kunz, A. Prasad, E. Pateromichelakis, K. Samdanis: Ultra-High Reliable 5G V2X Communications. *IEEE Commun. Stand. Mag.* 3(2), pp. 46-52 (2019)
16. S. Karnouskos, F. Kerschbaum: Privacy and Integrity Considerations in Hyperconnected Autonomous Vehicles. *Proc. IEEE* 106(1), pp. 160-170 (2018)
17. L. Vishwakarma, D. Das: SmartCoin: A novel incentive mechanism for vehicles in intelligent transportation system based on consortium blockchain. *Veh. Commun.* 33, article 100429 (2022)
18. D. Liu. Hyperledger-TWGC/tape: A simple traffic generator for Hyperledger Fabric (2020) <https://github.com/Hyperledger-TWGC/tape>
19. F. Poggenhans, J.H. Pauls, J. Janosovits, S. Orf, M. Naumann, F. Kuhnt, M. Mayr: Lanelet2: A high-definition map framework for the future of automated driving. In: *Proceedings of ITSC*, pp. 1672-1679 (2018)
20. M.B. Sinai, N. Partush, S. Yadid, E. Yahav: Exploiting Social Navigation. *CoRR* abs/1410.0151 (2014)
21. X. Sun, F.R. Yu, P. Zhang: A Survey on Cyber-Security of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs). *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.* 23(7), pp. 6240-6259 (2022)
22. M. Veres, M. Moussa: Deep Learning for Intelligent Transportation Systems: A Survey of Emerging Trends. *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.* 21(8), pp. 3152-3168 (2020)
23. H. Vardhan. HD Maps: New age maps Powering Autonomous vehicles (2019) <https://www.geospatialworld.net/article/hd-maps-autonomous-vehicles/>
24. Y. Yin, Y. Li, B. Ye, T. Liang, Y. Li: A Blockchain-Based Incremental Update Supported Data Storage System for Intelligent Vehicles. *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* 70(5), pp. 4880-4893 (2021)
25. Y. Yuan, F.Y. Wang: Towards blockchain-based intelligent transportation systems. In: *Proceedings of ITSC*, pp. 2663-2668 (2016)
26. A. Zang, Z. Li, D. Doria, G. Trajcevski: Accurate vehicle self-localization in high definition map dataset. In: *Proceedings of AutonomousGIS@SIGSPATIAL*, pp. 2:1-2:8 (2017)
27. L. Zhong, R. Onishi, L. Wang, L. Ruan, S.J. Tan: A Scalable Blockchain-based High-Definition Map Update Management System. In: *Proceedings of ISC2*, pp. 1-4 (2021)